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DAILY LIFE OF CRAFTSMEN IN TIMURIDS

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Abstract.

This article analyzes the craftsmen brought to the center during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, the conditions created for them by the government, based on historical sources and scientific literature. The class of craftsmen and their impact on the socio-economic life of the country are discussed.

Key words: Amir Temur, Timurids, craftsmen, Muhammad Naqqosh, "Boghi Shamol", Boysungur Mirzo, Boghi Dilkusho, exhibition, folk festivals, weddings, musician, carpenter.

Introduction. In the context of increasing globalization around the world, there is an increasing interest in studying the history of regions, preserving cultural heritage and strengthening it on the basis of national customs and traditions. In this regard, the issue of studying historical sources and manuscripts related to the economic, social, cultural and political management of each region at a certain historical stage, while maintaining its relevance, is one of the urgent tasks facing the science of history, including scientific research, and the development of practical proposals and recommendations for their effective use in today's conditions.

Literature analysis and method. The fact that Amir Temur paid special attention to issues of faith, education, and morality is covered in detail in historical works. In this regard, the works that allow us to study the personality of the great commander are "Nizamuddin Shami's "Zafarnama", "Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnama", "Samarkandga Amir Temur's Diary" by Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo (1403-1406), "Baburnama" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, "Ajoyib al-Maqdur fi Tarikhi Taimur (The Miracles of Fate in the History of Temur)" 1-2 books by Ibn Arabshah (1436-1437), "Matlai Sadayn va Majmai Bahrayn" by Abdurazzaq Samarqandi, and other works are of incomparable importance [1]. During the years of independence, on the occasion of the anniversaries of Amir Temur and Ulugbek, A. Orinbayev, A. Ahmedov, B. Ahmedov, T. Fayziyev, O. Buriyev and others translated written sources on the history of Amir Temur into

Uzbek and published a number of scientific studies and popular works. These scientific studies expressed a number of opinions on the issue [2].

Discussion and results. After the capture of Tabriz by Amir Temur, he sent craftsmen to Samarkand. During this period, craftsmen played a particularly important role in the construction of gardens. For example, in 1397, Amir Temur began the construction of the "Wind Garden" in the northern part of Samarkand. Its marble stones were brought from Tabriz. The craftsmen were Persian masters from Iraq. It was built for a month and a half. In 1397, Amir Temur ordered the construction of the Dilkusho Garden. Each side of it was 750 square meters. There was a dovecote inside the garden. In addition, he gave the garden to Tokal Khan, the daughter of Khizr Khoja Khan, and built a palace for her [3].

Skilled craftsmen were captured during the Indian campaign, and Amir Temur sent them to Samarkand. He saw the mosque in Firuzabad and decided to build such a mosque. In 1399, the construction of a mosque in Samarkand began on the instructions of Amir Temur. Stonemasons were brought from Azerbaijan, Persia, and India. 200 craftsmen were engaged in construction work, and 500 were engaged in cutting stones. 95 elephants were used to bring the stones. They made pillars from 480 stones, each of which was seven years old [4].

Most of the craftsmen from Damascus were also brought to Samarkand. The buildings in the city of Damascus were built of wood and stucco, and they burned down in a fire. They were mainly examples of painting. Amir Temur sent Shah Malikbek to protect the mosque from fire. However, it burned down. Only one minaret, known as the Arus Tower, or Bayza Tower, has survived. Of course, Amir Temur has nothing to do with it.

Baysungur Mirza, along with managing the affairs of the court, patronized all the nobles, craftsmen, and artists, assigned salaries, and gave gifts. However, the prince also fell ill due to his addiction to alcohol and died on December 20, 1433. The prince was buried in the Gavharshod Aga Madrasah. Saifuddin Naqqosh, who created under the pseudonym Vahidi, wrote a eulogy for his death:

No matter how many times this wheel has turned according to the era.

He could not find a single pattern on the porch of the era.

Whoever has eaten a morsel from the table of this era,

He must be a cupbearer of the wine of death.

Amir Temur associated the fate of his state with his grandchildren rather than his sons. Therefore, this is probably the reason why he attached great importance to their upbringing and education. Thanks to the order established

by his grandfather Timur, Baysungur Mirzo received a good education [5]. In particular, he constantly engaged in military exercises, wrote poems in Persian and Turkic, could predict the advantages of horses, participated in literary debates, participated in hunting, led the army in military campaigns, headed the Supreme Divan, understood music well, was an admirer of masters and calligraphers in the art of calligraphy and calligraphy. He constantly participated in weddings organized by representatives of the dynasty with the participation of craftsmen. A chortaq was built in the Zogan garden, the garden was decorated with Roman atlases and Chinese ornaments. The wonderful works of world engineers gathered in Herat were exhibited. 32 types of products produced in the workshop of Khoja Ali Orazigar Isfahani were also presented. Craftsmen such as a cotton cleaner, blacksmith, and carpenter participated. A grand wedding was organized on the occasion of the wedding of Sultan Ma'su Mirzo's sister. An exhibition was organized for the public. The prince's sister was engaged to Haydar Muhammad Mirzo, and their wedding took place in the "Bogi Zogon" [6]. Exhibitions were organized by craftsmen in the garden on the occasion of the wedding.

Khoja Mirak Naqqash is considered one of the great engravers. He was a master in the science of illustration and book decoration. No building or printed book in Herat passed through his hands. It happened between 1498-99. Muhammad Naqqash made efforts to produce Chinese porcelain here. The color and clarity of the dishes he made were unmatched. In addition, he invented a watch box in Navoi's library. Later, offended by Navoi, he entered the service of Badiuzzaman Mirzo [7].

Conclusions. The reign of during Amir Temur and the Timurids, great attention was paid to craftsmen. They were assigned sufficient salaries and improved living conditions. Skilled craftsmen were brought from different regions, and they founded their own schools here.

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